

3,4-Coumarino-pyrones. Part I. Synthesis of some 3,4-Coumarino- α -pyrones

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Some 3,4-coumarino- α -pyrones have been synthesised by condensing 4-hydroxycoumarin, 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin, and 4-hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin with ethylacetoacetate and with ethyl α -methylacetoacetate, the condensations taking place smoothly in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The optimum yields of coumarino- α -pyrones (as high as 80% in some cases) are obtained when a large excess of β -ketonic ester is used in the reaction.

With 80% H_2SO_4 (at room temperature) or $POCl_3$ as the condensing agent, the same coumarino- α -pyrones have been obtained in poor yields. The condensations of these 4-hydroxycoumarins with ethyl α -methylacetoacetate could not be effected in presence of these condensing agents.

Condensations of 4-hydroxy-(Ia), 4-hydroxy-6-methyl-(Ib), and 4-hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin (Ic) with ethylacetoacetate to provide the respective 3,4-coumarino- α -pyrones (IIa, IIb and IIc: $Y=H$) were reported by us in a preliminary communication¹. The same 4-hydroxycoumarins (Ia, Ib, and Ic) have now been condensed successfully with ethyl α -methylacetoacetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to afford coumarino-(3',4',5,6)-3,4 dimethyl- α -pyrone (IIa: $Y=Me$), coumarino (3',4',5,6)-3,4,6'-trimethyl- α -pyrone (IIb: $Y=Me$), and coumarino(3',4',5,6)-3,4,8'-trimethyl- α -pyrone (IIc: $Y=Me$) respectively. The alternative possibility of these compounds to be 2-methyl- γ -pyrone derivatives (III) was ruled out as these failed to condense with piperonal in presence of sodium ethoxide (a characteristic property of 2-methyl- γ -pyrones²).

(a) $R=R'=H$. (b) $R=H$; $R'=Me$. (c) $R=Me$; $R'=H$

All the 3,4-coumarino- α -pyrones synthesised dissolved in 10% aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide on warming on a water bath and could be reprecipitated unchanged on

1. Patell and Usgaonkar, *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, 32, 406.

2. Heilborn *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2559; King and Robertson, *ibid.*, 1934, 403; Chakravarti, *this Journal*, 1931, 8, 129; 1936, 13, 619.

acidification. The coumarino- α -pyrones (IIa: Y=H), (IIb: Y=H), and (IIc: Y=H) on refluxing with 20% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution for 3 hr. were degraded with rupture of both the heterocyclic rings to provide salicylic acid (IVa), *p*-cresotic acid (IVb), and *o*-cresotic acid (IVc), respectively, which were identified by taking mixed m.p. with the authentic specimens.

Condensations of 4-hydroxycoumarins (Ia, Ib, and Ic) with ethyl acetoacetate took place very smoothly in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, affording very good yields of the respective coumarino- α -pyrones (II: Y=H). The optimum yields (as high as 80%) were obtained when the coumarin derivative, β -ketonic ester, and anhydrous aluminium chloride were used in the molar proportion of 1:3:2; a large excess of β -ketonic ester in the reaction thus favoured the condensations. It is interesting to note that with theoretically required amount of β ketonic ester, the yield of coumarino- α -pyrones decreases considerably and a large amount of unchanged coumarin derivative could be recovered.

4-Hydroxycoumarins (Ia, Ib, and Ic) failed to condense with ethyl α -methylacetoacetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride when theoretically required amount of the ester (*i.e.* 1 mole of ester per mole of coumarin derivative) was used in the reaction. The same 4-hydroxycoumarins, however, condensed smoothly when the coumarin derivative, the ester, and anhydrous aluminium chloride were used in the molar proportion of 1:3:2 as before. The yields of coumarino- α -pyrones were, however, comparatively very low (20%). Increase in the amount of anhydrous aluminium chloride in the reaction did not much affect the condensation.

The condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarins (Ia, Ib, and Ic) with β -ketonic ester in presence either of 80% sulphuric acid or phosphorus oxychloride did not take place satisfactorily. The coumarin derivatives condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of 80% sulphuric acid (at room temp.) and also in presence of phosphorus oxychloride to provide the same coumarino- α -pyrone (II: Y=H) as obtained in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, but the yields were very poor. Ethyl α -methylacetoacetate, however, did not at all condense with these 4-hydroxycoumarins in presence of these condensing agents. Soon after publication of our preliminary, note², Mustafa *et al.*³, also reported the condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin(Ia) with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid, obtaining the same coumarino- α -pyrone (IIa: Y=H) that had been reported by us¹. They, however, carried out the reaction at 100° and reported an yield of 55%. Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Coumarino(3',4', 5,6)-4-methyl- α -pyrone (IIa: Y=H).—4-Hydroxycoumarin⁴ (Ia) (3.3g., 1M) and ethyl acetoacetate (7.8 g., 3M) were added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.4 g., 2M) in dry nitrobenzene (24 ml) and the reaction mixture was heated at 130° in an oil bath for 4 hr. Crushed ice and HCl (conc.) were added and the nitrobenzene removed by steam distillation. The residual solid, after trituration with sodium

3. *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 1831.

4. Shah *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, 25, 667.

bicarbonate solution to remove any unchanged original coumarin, was washed with water and crystallised from benzene in silky needles, m.p. 245-46°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 68.63; H, 3.90. $C_{13}H_8O_4$ requires C, 68.40; H, 3.50%). UV absorption in MeOH: λ_{max} 255, 265, 335, and 345 (log ϵ , 3.91, 3.92, 4.00, and 3.99).

When ethyl acetoacetate (2.6 g., 1M) was used in the above condensation, the yield of coumarino- α -pyrone obtained was 2.0 g. and with ethyl acetoacetate (5.2g., 2M) in the condensation, the yield of the coumarino- α -pyrone was 2.8-3.0 g.

In presence of Sulphuric Acid.—The coumarin (Ia) (1.6 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (4 g.), and 80% H_2SO_4 (7ml) were mixed together and the mixture after keeping at the room temperature for 48 hr. was poured on crushed ice. The crude product, after triturating with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove any unchanged 4-hydroxycoumarin, was washed and crystallised from benzene in needles; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above sample, 245-46°; yield 0.16 g. (Ia) recovered was 0.8 g.

In presence of Phosphorus Oxychloride.—The coumarin (Ia) (1g.), ethyl acetoacetate (2.4 g.), $POCl_3$ (3 ml) were mixed and the mixture was heated at 70-75° for 4 hr. It was then poured on crushed ice when a sticky solid separated. After triturating it with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the unchanged coumarin, it was crystallised from benzene in needles (0.32 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. with previous sample, 245-46°.

Action of Sodium Hydroxide Solution.—The coumarino- α -pyrone (1 g.) was refluxed with an aqueous 20% NaOH solution (30 ml) for 3 hr. The solution after cooling was acidified when a crystalline solid separated. It was recrystallised from water, m.p. 158-59°. It was identified as salicylic acid (IVa, m.p. 159°). Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of the same showed no depression.

Coumarino(3',4', 5,6)-3,4-dimethyl- α -pyrone (IIb: Y = Me).—4-Hydroxycoumarin (Ia) (1.6 g.) and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (4.3 g.) were added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.7 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (12 ml) and the mixture was heated at 130° for 4 hr. Crushed ice and HCl (conc.) were then added and nitrobenzene was removed. The resulting sticky solid was triturated with NaOH solution (dil.), washed, dried, and crystallised from benzene (charcoal) in needles, m.p. 217-18°, yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 69.50; H, 4.60. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 69.41; H, 4.13%).

Coumarino(3',4',5, 6)-4, 6'-dimethyl- α -pyrone (IIb: Y=H).—4-Hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin⁴ (Ib) (3.5 g., 1M) and ethyl acetoacetate (7.8 g., 3M) were added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.4 g., 2M) in dry nitrobenzene (24 ml); the reaction mixture was heated at 130° for 4 hr. and then worked up as usual. The crude product obtained was crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 197-98°, yield 4.2 g. (Found: C, 69.50; H, 4.40. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 69.41; H, 4.13%) UV absorption in MeOH: λ_{max} 260, 270, 280, 335, and 347 (log ϵ , 3.93, 3.94, 3.92, 3.92, and 3.91). When ethyl acetoacetate (2.6g., 1M) was used in the above reaction, the yield of the coumarino- α -pyrone was 2.3 g.

The condensation of (Ib) (1.8 g.) with ethyl acetoacetate (4.0 g.) in presence of 80% H_2SO_4 (7 ml) at the room temperature for 48 hr., as in the previous case, furnished the same coumarino- α -pyrone (IIb: Y=H); m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, 197-98°; yield 0.02 g. (Ib), recovered was 1.2g.

The condensation of (Ib) (1.1 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (2.4 g.) in presence of POCl_3 (3 ml) at $70-75^\circ$ for 4 hr. also afforded the same coumarino- α -pyrone (IIb: $\text{Y}=\text{H}$) (yield 0.03 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, $197-98^\circ$. The reaction was worked up as in the previous case.

Action of Sodium Hydroxide Solution.—The coumarino- α -pyrone (IIb: $\text{Y}=\text{H}$) (1 g.) was refluxed with an aqueous 20% NaOH solution (30 ml) for 3 hr., cooled, and acidified. The crystalline substance separating was recrystallised from water, m.p. $148-49^\circ$. It was identified as *p*-cresotic acid (IVb, m.p. 151°). Mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen of the same showed no lowering.

Coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-3, 4, 6'-trimethyl- α -pyrone (IIb: $\text{Y}=\text{Me}$).—4-Hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ib) (1.76 g.) and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (4.3 g.) were added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.7 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (12 ml) and heated at 130° for 4 hr. Ice and HCl (conc.) were added and the nitrobenzene was removed. The sticky black solid residue was triturated with NaOH solution (dil.) to remove the unchanged coumarin. It was washed and crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in needles, m.p. $214-15^\circ$, yield 0.32 g. (Found: C, 70.3; H, 5.1; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 70.3; H, 4.7%).

Coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4, 8'-dimethyl- α -pyrone (IIc: $\text{Y}=\text{H}$).—4-Hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin⁴ (Ic) (3.5 g., 1M) and ethyl acetoacetate (7.8 g., 3M) were added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.4 g., 2M) in dry nitrobenzene (24 ml) and heated at 130° for 4 hr. and worked up as above. The product was crystallised from benzene in thin plates, m.p. $202-203^\circ$, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C 68.9; H, 4.4. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires, C, 69.41; H, 4.13%). U V absorption in MeOH: λ_{max} 270, 335, and 345 ($\log \epsilon$, 4.02, 4.01, and 4.03). When ethyl acetoacetate (2.6 g., 1M) was used in the reaction, the yield of the coumarino- α -pyrone was 1.9 g.

The coumarin (Ic) (1.76 g.) was condensed with ethyl acetoacetate (4 g.) in presence of 80% H_2SO_4 (7 ml) by keeping at the room temperature for 48 hr. On working up the reaction mixture as usual, the same coumarino- α -pyrone (IIb: $\text{Y}=\text{H}$) was obtained; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, $202-203^\circ$; yield 0.13 g. (Ic) recovered was 0.6 g.

The condensation of (Ic) (1.1 g.) with ethyl acetoacetate (2.4 g.) in presence of POCl_3 (3 ml) at $70-75^\circ$ in the usual manner afforded the same coumarino- α -pyrone (IIc: $\text{Y}=\text{H}$); m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above specimen, $202-203^\circ$, yield 0.02 g.

Action of Sodium Hydroxide Solution.—The coumarino- α -pyrone (IIc: $\text{Y}=\text{H}$) was refluxed with an aqueous 20% NaOH solution (30 ml) for 3 hr. On acidification, a crystalline substance separated. It was recrystallised from water in needles, m.p. $164-65^\circ$. It was identified as *o*-cresotic acid (IVc, m.p. $163-64^\circ$). Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of the same showed no lowering.

Coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-3, 4, 8'-trimethyl- α -pyrone (IIc: $\text{Y}=\text{Me}$).—4-Hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin (Ic) (1.76 g.) and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (4.3 g.) were added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.7 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (12 ml) and heated at 130° for 4 hr. Ice and HCl (conc.) were added and the nitrobenzene was removed. The sticky,

black solid remaining behind was triturated with a dilute NaOH solution, washed, and crystallised from ethanol (charcoal) in needles, m.p. 220-21°, yield 0.29 g. (Found C, 70.0; H, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.3; H 4.7%).

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